

SUNSCREEN OVERVIEW-API AND THEIR EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

Sunscreens are necessary to shield skin from ultraviolet (UV) light's harmful effects, as burns from the sun, early aging, and an increased chance of developing skin cancer. This review explores the key active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and excipients in sunscreen formulations, emphasizing their contributions to Sun Protection Factor (SPF) and Persistent Pigment Darkening (PPD) measurements. SPF is a crucial indicator of a sunscreen's capacity in order to avoid UVB-induced damage, while PPD assesses its effectiveness in protecting against UVA related harm. Chemical UV filters, such as avobenzone and oxybenzone, function through taking in UV radiation and converting it into heat, whereas physical filters, like zinc oxide and titanium dioxide, reflect and scatter UV rays. The use of these filters, along with other APIs, is critical for broad-spectrum protection. However, each type has its advantages and potential downsides, such as skin sensitivity or environmental concerns, which must be considered during formulation. The purpose of this article is to offer a thorough analysis of the interactions between APIs, excipients, SPF, and PPD in sunscreen products. It also evaluates their overall benefits and drawbacks, offering insights into the development of sunscreens that are effective, safe, and environmentally responsible.

KEYWORDS: Sunscreen, sun protection, UVA filters, UVB filters, Avobenzone, Oxybenzone, Octocrylene, Zinc oxide, Titanium dioxide.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sunlight promotes vitamin D production and β -endorphin expression, improving overall well-being. However, excessive sunlight exposure causes photo-induced skin damage, including skin cancer, sun damage, excessive pigmentation, photosensitization, and sunburn(1). The sun produces visible light, ultraviolet (UV), and infrared (IR) radiation, among other types of radiation(2). Skin cancer cases are rising and seem to be a public health issue. International health authorities have responded to this issue by advising people to adopt protective precautions against UV radiation's detrimental effects. Broad-spectrum UV skin protection is offered by sunscreens, which also frequently include UV filter combinations. It is commonly known that they are effective in lowering the risk of skin photoaging and carcinogenesis. Sunscreen products are an excellent substitute for protecting the skin from UV ray damage. Organic (chemical compounds) or inorganic (mineral compounds) UV filters can be added to sunscreen formulas. To provide the best level of UV protection, modern sunscreens combine a number of UV filters, both inorganic and organic, to offer comprehensive UV spectrum protection(3). Sunscreens are commercial products that are intended to protect human skin from ultraviolet radiation. They can include one or more UVFs, which can be chemical, physical, or both. Sunscreens also contain a variety of other ingredients, including fragrances, emulsifiers, emollients, and colouring compounds(5). There are various concerns about the toxicity of organic UV filters, including detrimental cell damage and biological function disruptions(4). Regardless, exposure to natural UV sunshine has positive effects on human health because it helps the skin to produce endorphins and synthesise vitamin D(12). The Sun Protection Factor (SPF) is a commonly used indicator of sunscreen efficiency. The first stage in the approach is to determine the minimum erythematous dose (MED), which is the least amount of energy needed to induce erythema in both protected and exposed skin (15). The sun protection factor (SPF), which is the ratio of UV radiation needed to create a minimal erythematous dose (MED) in protective skin to exposed skin, is typically used to determine how effective sunscreen is(6). Sunscreen agents permeate the skin, reducing their effectiveness and safety, generating systemic circulation and unknown side effects(7). Friedrich Hammer produced the first monograph on photobiology in 1891, discussing the application of several products to avoid sunburn. In 1928, the USA saw the commercial release of the first sunscreen(14).

2. SUNSCREEN

Sunscreens' primary purpose is to prevent skin cancer by absorbing and/or dispersing UV rays(22). Sunscreens are a therapeutic tool that dermatologists are always adding to their toolkit[23]. The components found in photoprotector formulae that directly interfere with incident solar radiation through energy absorption, reflection, or dispersion are known as ultraviolet filters, or sunscreens(24). As of right now, Australia's

Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA) has approved 33 active compounds for use in sunscreens(25). Sunscreen can also be roughly classified into topical and systemic categories based on how it is applied. A multi-component sunscreen has common coatings to stop bleaching and colour fading as well as active ingredients to protect UV rays. Many UV filters can be found in sunscreen formulations(26). Sunscreen products seem very straightforward on the surface. They are made up of a delivery vehicle that holds one or more active components for sunscreen. These sunscreen ingredients work by blocking solar ultraviolet (UV) radiation before they have a chance to harm the skin beneath(27). Before the present era of drug review, sunscreens were first approved as over-the-counter (OTC) drugs, suggested for the prevention of sunburn(28). It has been demonstrated that applying a high sun protection factor (SPF) sunscreen once can prevent sunburn; however, the possibility of further protection after reapplying sunscreen has not received much attention(29). For sunscreen agents, there are three widely accepted names in the world. These are the trade name, the US adopted name (USAN), and the International Nomenclature Cosmetic Ingredient (INCI) name. Using avobenzone (USAN), which is the INCI name for avobenzone, as an example(23). As of right now, Australia's Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA) has approved 33 active compounds for use in sunscreens. Sunscreen components are separated into two categories: inorganic (which includes synthetic organic compounds) and organic(24). Organic sunscreens are classified into UVB and UVA filters:

2.1 UVB filters: PABA derivatives - Padimate O Cinnamates - Octinoxate, Cinoxate; Salicylates - Octisalate, Homosalate, Trolamine salicylate, Octocrylene Ensulizole.

2.2 UVA filters: Benzophenones (UVB and UVA2 absorbers) - Oxybenzone, Sulisobenzene, Dioxybenzone, Avobenzone or Parsol 1789 (UVA1 absorber), Meradimate(UVA2 absorber)(23).

Fig.1 (13)

3.SUN PROTECTION FACTOR (SPF)

The Sun Protection Factor (SPF), which is really a new nomenclature for the well-known "Schulze method," was first used by Greiter in 1974. Greiter's proposed the Sun Protection Factor and gained global recognition and usage very rapidly. However, the method's lack of standardization resulted in a wide range of numerical values found and employed in sunscreens, making it unreliable. According to the FDA's 1978 proposal, the Sun Protection Factor, The minimal erythemal dose (MED) of skin protected by sunscreen, applied at a rate of 2 mg/cm², and the lowest erythemal dose of skin unprotected by sunscreen are divided by 26. The following equation can be used to express this mathematical relationship: $spf = \text{MED (protected skin)} / \text{MED (unprotected skin)}$ (15). It is known that individuals with lower minimal erythemal dose (MED) values have greater SPF values for sunscreen(16). A perfect sunscreen evaluation system would take UVB and UVA protection into account. Nonetheless, the primary factor in determining the effectiveness of sunscreens should still be the SPF rating(17). Ten years ago, an SPF of 15 was thought to provide an absolute barrier against ultraviolet (UV) light. The reasoning behind the cutoff threshold was that erythema would always be prevented by sunscreens with this SPF value, and erythema prevention would stop all the negative consequences of UV exposure. This indicates that less than half of the SPF stated on the label is actually applied to the customer's skin. As a result, a sunscreen with an SPF of 30 will actually provide SPF 15 protection(18). Investigation supports the use of sun protection factors (SPFs) in the avoidance of UV-induced skin alterations, including melanoma and squamous cell carcinoma(19). Currently, the greatest trustworthy information available to consumers on the efficiency of sunscreen filters is the sun protection factor (20). Many people mistakenly believe that SPF 60 is not twice as protective as SPF 30.(we must add, at least when it comes to avoiding sunburn in lab settings). According to the reasoning, an SPF 30 sunscreen blocks out 96.7% of erythemogenic UV rays, while an SPF 60 sunscreen blocks out 98.3%, or just 1.6%(21). The formula used to compute the SPF ($\text{SPF MED with sunscreen} / \text{SPF MED without sunscreen}$)(35)

3.1 Table (41)

SPF Value	Protection function
SPF 6	It gives minimum protection.
SPF 10	It gives minimum protection
SPF 15	It gives medium protection
SPF 20	It gives medium protection
SPF 25	It gives great protection
SPF 30	It gives great protection
SPF 50	It gives great protection
SPF 50+	It gives very high protection

4.PROTECTION FACTOR OF UVA

The ultraviolet spectrum, which is split into three parts by UVC (200–290 nm), UVB (290–320 nm), and UVA (320–400 nm), makes up a portion of the sunlight that reaches the earth in this earth's atmosphere absorbs all UVC radiation and more than 20 times as much UVA reaches the ground than UVB. It was once believed that UVA wavelengths (320–400 nm) only contributed significantly to skin aging. However, more recent scientific studies have revealed that UVA can also produce malignant keratinocyte cells in the deep layer of the epidermis and cause cells to release more inflammatory proteins, such as IL10, TNF α , IL1 α , IL6, and IL8 are among the inflammatory proteins whose expression is also elevated by it. With the assistance of ROS (reactive oxygen species), also it contributes significantly to the alteration of mitochondrial DNA in human skin .so the product must have ability to defend against UVA is crucial in addition to UVB ray protection(42). There are many different formulations of sunscreens available, including lotions, creams, gels, aerosol sprays, etc. All therapeutic sunscreens, regardless of kind, must meet three labelling requirements: the broad spectrum test, the water resistance test, and the Sun protection Factor (SPF) test. Sunscreens bearing the label "broad spectrum" provide stronger protection because The term "broad spectrum" suggests that the sunscreen shields the skin from both UVA and UVB rays(41).

4.1 Testing methods for UVA-PF

The UVA protection factor (UVA-PF), which may be determined using two methods: immediate pigment darkening (IPD) and persistent pigment darkening (PPD), is used to assess the UVA protection efficacy of sunscreen products(41). Since persistent pigment darkening is caused by UVA radiation rather than UVB, the Persistent Pigment Darkening (PPD) approach is likely the most used technique to calculate UVA protection factor (UVAPF). With the following exceptions, the UVAPF and SPF are calculated on human volunteers in a comparable manner: PPD will be the endpoint rather than erythema, volunteers will have a prototype and be able to develop instantaneous pigmentation (phototypes III and IV). A UVA source will be employed in place of a full solar simulated radiation exposure. The UVA protection improves with a higher UVAPF value(43). PPD-PF of 2-4 is given a rating of PA+, PPD-PF of 4-8 is given a rating of PA++, PPD-PF of 8-16 is given a rating of PA+++, and PPD-PF of 16 or more is given a rating of PA++++. These ratings are part of the Protection Grade of UVA (PA) grading system that is used in Asian countries. Because PPD requires a higher UVA dose and a longer exposure period than IPD, sunscreen stability is also questioned during a PPD test (41). Another method for the determination of UVAPF is crucial wavelength method, is an additional strategy. This technique solely considers the UV absorption spectrum's form, not its amplitude. As a result, it makes sure that items absorb in the long UVA waveband without assessing the degree of UVA protection(43). In Europe, a minimum standard for sunscreens' UVA efficacy was selected in 2006.[12] The product must now have a UVAPF of at least 1/3 of its SPF, or an SPF/UVAPF ratio of ≤ 3 . Recently, Australia and the Mercosur nations—Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay—have also embraced this criterion. In India the majority of Indians have Fitzpatrick skin phototypes IV to V, these calculations indicate that sunscreens in India should also have an SPF/UVAPF ratio of less than 3. The calculations were based on seasonal meteorological daily doses and weighted by various factors, including skin type, anatomical skin area, realistic sunscreen use conditions, and realistic UVR exposure duration. The result shows that a high level of UVA protection is needed in Asia. In India, the minimum UVAPF required is 12–17 in the winter and the maximum is 29–30 in the summer, which highlights the need for a well-balanced UVB UVA protection(43). To prevent having high UVB protection and poor UVA protection, an appropriate ratio between UVA and UVB protection Levels ought to be preserved. For consumer protection to be compatible, all countries should use the European Commission's definition of an SPF/UVAPF ratio of no more than 3:1. It takes a variety of UV filters to provide balanced protection. The following factors were used to choose this combination: To cover the full UV spectrum, UV filter needs to have distinct maximum absorbance

peaks (UVB, short UVA, and long UVA). Additionally, filters should be selected based on the lipophilic and hydrophilic phases of the sunscreen emulsion. Finally, The mixture needs to be able to be photostable(44).

5.UV FILTER

Humans are concerned about ultraviolet (UV) rays due to their detrimental effects on skin. While UVA and UVB radiation are capable of reaching the surface of the Earth, they can have harmful effects. Based on their wavelength, UV rays are separated into three regions: UV radiation (UVA, UVB, and UVC). Sunscreens and UV filters are essential due to UV radiation's detrimental effects on human skin. On the market, UV filters fall into two groups: organic (chemical) and inorganic (physical). Their behaviour is influenced by their makeup, which is the basis of its classification(8). The ultraviolet Within the electromagnetic spectrum are wavelengths, involving between visible light and gamma radiation. UVA light, which ranges from 320 to 400 nm, is the least energetic type. UVC photons are made up of wavelengths between 100 and 280 nm, while UVB photons are made up of wavelengths between 280 and 320 nm. Occasionally, UVA is divided into UVA1 (320–340 nm) and UVA2(340-400 nm)(13). Sunscreens with UV filters are frequently seen in pharmaceutical personal care products (PPCPs) and food product packaging due to their ability to lessen the harm that UV (UVB and UVA) radiation may cause(12).

5.1 Organic filter

Organic ultraviolet The usage of (UV) filters in the cosmetics industry is common and are known to be a broad set of chemicals that are efficient against the increasing incidence of skin malignancies. UVA (benzophenones, anthranilates, and dibenzoylmethane) and UVB (PABA derivatives, salicylates, cinnamates, and camphor derivatives) are the two categories into which chemical organic filters are divided(9). organic uv filters contain Octocrylene, Octinoxate, Avobenzone, Ecamsule, Oxybenzone, Octisalate, Homosalate, Padimate, Ensulizole, Dioxibenzone, Meradimate, Benzophenone-1, Trolamine salicylate, Aminobenzoic acid(4,11). The ultraviolet (UV) filters that are most frequently used in sunscreens and cosmetics are oxybenzone, avobenzone, octocrylene ,and octinoxate. These compounds are classified as " high-volume chemicals produced" with the European Union producing N1000 metric tons of them annually(12). It is well known that Organic UV filters can trigger allergies contact dermatitis. An allergic response on the skin to light that is mediated by contact with specific chemical substances is known as photoallergic contact dermatitis(3).

Table 5.1.1(3,4)

Organic uv filter	solubility	Range
Avobenzone	lipophilic	UVA1
Octocrylene	lipophilic	UVB
Benzophenone 3	lipophilic	UVB
Homosalate	lipophilic	UVB
Para-aminobenzoic acid	hydrophilic	UVB

5.2 Inorganic filter

Inorganic sunscreens have become more and more common in beach and everyday photoprotection products during the past ten years. Their efficacy and safety, especially when it comes to shielding UVA rays, have played a significant role in Typically, these inorganic sunscreens considered innocuous pigments that stay outside of the skin, in contrast to organic sunscreens, which may be affected by light radiation. The two inorganic sunscreens that are most frequently utilized are zinc oxide (ZnO) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂). (11). As a result, when it comes to photoprotection, inorganic UV filters like zinc oxide (ZnO) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are now essential. ZnO's UVA-UVB absorption curve is broad nonetheless, TiO₂ provides better UVB protection. Based on available data, sunscreens containing zinc oxide (ZnO) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are secure substitutes for people who are worried about growing proof of the environmental effect of organic UV filters(14). Table 5.2.1(3,4)

Inorganic uv filter	function	Range
Titanium dioxide	Reflect UVA and UVB	UVB,UVA2
Zinc oxide	Reflect UVA and UVB	UVB ,UVA1, UVA2.

6.ACTIVE INGREDIENTS

Sunscreen contain active ingredients called UV filters, which can be soluble or non soluble. Examples of non soluble filters, often known as mineral or physical filters, are zinc oxide and titanium dioxide. As such, they fall within the category of physical sunscreens. However, because soluble filters, also referred to as organic or chemical filters, contain a number of chemicals, including octinoxate and oxybenzone, they are classified as chemical sunscreens(36,37).

6.1 AVOBENZONE

Avobenzone is included as an active component in sunscreens by the European Chemical Agency's list of approved UV filters under the Cosmetics Products Regulation and the Federal Drug Administration's (FDA) 1999 Sunscreen Drug Product Monograph for Over-the-Counter Human Usage(33).Chemically recognized as 1-(4-tertbutylphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)propane, avobenzone frequently referred to as methoxydibenzoylmethane. It is an extremely powerful UVA filter. Its capacity to take in a broad The spectrum of photons in UVA, particularly the UVA I spectrum, has made it one of the most well-known UVA filters; the greatest reach their highest of absorption occurs at 357 nm ($\epsilon = 34,140 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$). Sunscreens are widely used because they provide broad-spectrum protection against UV rays when avobenzone is added to the mix(30).the effects of concentration, skin surface temperature, and solvent (including emollients) on the excited state relaxation mechanism of avobenzone have been studied using ultrafast transient electronic absorption spectroscopy (TEAS), which has been used to estimate the photostability of the drug after photoexcitation with UVA radiation (approximately 350 nm)(31). An analysis of the development of sunscreen products in the United States reveals that the initially of dibenzoyl methane derivatives—of which avobenzone is the majority well known—was a specific response to the need to defend against UVA irradiation (315–400nm)(33). One common contact allergen is butyl methoxy dibenzoyl methane; nevertheless, ACD is less frequently reported than PACD(37). Due to its demonstrated ability to enhance UV protection, the avobenzone derivative has shown promise as a sunscreen component. It reduces the phototoxic potential of avobenzone and octyl methoxycinnamate, a combination of photo unstable UV filters, by efficiently photo stabilizing them in solution and formulation(62).Toxicity of avobenzone in plants: Avobenzone (AVO) is continuously discharged into the environment. Wastewater is present in the soil because it is used for irrigation, leaches from cultivated soils, and is combined with sewage biosolids for fertilization. Along with a Mito depressive impact, modifications to the mitotic spindle, and a decrease in the root growth of *Allium cepa* bulbs, it also resulted in a decrease in the root growth of *Cucumis sativus* and *Allium cepa* seeds. avobenzone (AVO) disarmed the root meristems' enzymatic Defence mechanism, which resulted in a buildup of superoxides and hydroxyl radicals in addition to lipid peroxidation in cells, disrupting the cell cycle. AVO has a strong potential to harm plants, and it may have a detrimental impact on both the growth of untamed plants and agricultural output(32). The sunlight absorption of avobenzone in DMSO and sunscreen formulations was investigated in this work since the compound photo isomerized in keto form when dissolved in solution(40).Modification of Tyrosine Phosphorylation and Protein Kinase A activity: In addition to being found in human urine and blood, this UV filter has been reported to be readily exposed in swimming pools and beaches. Human fecundity and fertility are linked to decreased exposure to these endocrine disruptors via different mechanisms. In this sense, even though AVO is a recognized endocrine disruptor, nothing is known about its effects on male reproduction and its toxicity outside of specific aquatic organisms. Consequently, we assessed the impact of AVO on a number of sperm activities in this work, including the measurement of tyrosine phosphorylation and protein kinase A (PKA) activity, which are crucial signaling processes during capacitation(63).

6.2 OXYBENZONE

Oxybenzone, also known as benzophenone-3(bp-3), is a member of the aromatic ketone family, or benzophenones, which have been widely used for the creation of sunscreens for the creation of sunscreen for nearly fifty years(64). according to oxybenzone, the primary process for the effective photoprotection it provides is based on a rapid enol keto tautomerization that is followed by a non-diabetic transition to the ground electronic state. The initial enol tautomer is then reformed by further collisions with the solvent solution(65).it has recently demonstrated that oxybenzone, the active component of most sunscreen, is poisonous to people, coral reefs, and other creatures. This is the first study to show that the oxybenzone can dramatically reduce respiration and photosynthesis in the leaves of a higher plant, cucumber. Cucumber respiration and photosynthesis were clearly decreased by an oxybenzone solution level as low as 0.2 to 28 mg/L. In cucumber leaves, oxybenzone quickly blocks the electron transport of the mitochondria and chloroplast(66). SIR Cameron Hayden and colleagues, demonstrate oxybenzone skin penetration from a commercially available SPF 15+ sunscreen cream. The formulation contains 6% oxybenzone among other active components. They come to the conclusion that applying oxybenzone to a broad surface area repeatedly and for prolonged periods of time is not advised. The conclusions drawn by Hayden and colleagues are not justified. Based on an evaluation of safety data and a history of safe usage spanning more than 30 years, international regulatory bodies have approved the maximum dosage of oxybenzone containing sunscreen are widely used very few negative side effects primarily contact or photo contact allergies have been documented(67).After a week, their were no clinically significant changes in thyroid hormone levels. This suggests that, at least for the brief period of the trial, the maximum permissible concentration of BP-3 in sunscreen was not able to upset the thyroid hormone homeostasis. Despite the use of many metrics to measure fertility, there was no correlation found between BP-3 concentration. The impact on the development of pubertal is unclear(68). Numerous investigations conducted on animals have shown that exposure to benzophenone (also known as oxybenzone) compounds disrupt the hypothalamic pituitary gonadal system, and androgen receptors. Oxybenzone has been detected in human urine, serum, and breast milk at detectable amounts the usage of sunscreen is thought to be the cause of this(34).some worry that the use of oxybenzone in sun protection factor (SPF) products may be prohibited in Hawaii, eliminating an effective UV absorber and perhaps increasing the number of skin cancer cases reported each year. However a sunscreen product's capacity to block UV rays is not dependent on any one element in its formula; rather, it is determined by the formula's overall performance when evaluated in accordance with the Food and drug Administration (FDA) criteria for labelling and efficacy testing(69). The levels of oxybenzone and other widely used UV filters were assessed in subterranean water samples and in the sands from Hanauma bay's beach shower sites. The findings suggest environmental pollution from beach showers. According to hydrodynamic modelling, oxybenzone pollution in the water of Hanauma Bay may be preserved for a duration of 14 to 50 hours following a single discharge event. Two distinct Hazard and Risk assessment evaluation, concentrating solely on oxybenzone, were carried out to ascertain the threat posed by oxybenzone to the coral reef system in Hanauma bay(70).photoallergic or persistent eczema on skin regions exposed to sunlight and in touch with the material is the primary clinical symptoms. Two diagnostic methods are needed for photo allergy; the photo test (used in photodermatology) and the patch (used for contact dermatitis). Since the PP test is not widely used, PACD is thought to be uncommon. Our findings about the proportion of patients who have oxybenzone photoallergy are in line with those that have been published in Colombia(71).

6.3 OCTOCRYLENE

octocrylene It is the chemically equivalent of 2-cyano-3,3-diphenylacrylic acid's 2-ethylhexyl ester. As long as the concentration stays below 10%, it is authorized in the EU and deemed safe in a variety of goods, including creams, lotions, pump sprays, face or hand creams, and lipsticks. Products that use propellant spray have a maximum concentration of 9%(30).At a maximum concentration of 10%, octocrylene (OC), an ester from the cinnamates family, is found in sunscreen and cosmetics for everyday use(33). Few research has been done on its toxicity and accumulation to date, particularly in aquatic organisms(36). The literature contains a significant number of ACD and PACD reactions to octocrylene. Octocrylene was the most common photo allergen in a multicenter photo patch study conducted across Europe with 1031 patients.(37). In addition to its potential for causing allergies and/or photoallergic reactions, octocrylene has lately been linked to negative effects on the endocrine system(39). It is an organic ultraviolet (UV) filter that primarily absorbs short UVA wavelengths and UVB radiation. Because of its capacity to absorb UV radiation, Sunscreens contain in conjunction with other UV filters to reach an appropriate sun protection factor (SPF). Additionally, it is employed in the stabilization of

other UV filters, such as avobenzone, which is especially useful against UVA2. Octocrylene has been linked to endocrine disruption and has the potential to induce allergies and/or (photo)allergies(39). Octocrylene appears to be a powerful allergen that induces contact dermatitis in most cases and photoallergic contact dermatitis in children, especially in adults with a history of photoallergy from ketoprofen. Octocrylene photopatch test results are often positive in patients with ketoprofen-induced photoallergy. It is necessary to tell these patients about sunscreen creams that do not include benzophenone-3 or octocrylene(59). A review of cosmetic compound-induced contact urticaria was published recently. The only component of sunscreen that was discovered to occasionally result in anaphylaxis and contact urticaria was benzophenone-3. Callus urticaria brought induced by octocrylene(60). The survival of certain species that rely on the soil either directly or indirectly may be adversely affected by the presence of octocrylene(61).

6.4 TITANIUM DIOXIDE

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles are widely used in cosmetics, especially sunscreens, because they can absorb UV light. These days, many pharmaceutical and cosmetic products contain nanoparticles(45). Titanium dioxide exhibits as rutile, anatase, brookite crystallographic forms and also possess + 4, + 3, + 2 oxidation states. It is a white solid powder, insoluble in water with 4.23 g/cm³, 79.866 g/mol of relative density and molecular weight respectively(46). Sunscreens have historically contained TiO₂ and ZnO due to their UVA and UVB filtration properties(50). These days, many pharmaceutical and cosmetic items use nanoparticles in their pharmaceutical products. The rutile crystal form of titanium dioxide is the most commonly utilized form that is appropriate for UV filtering. Both rutile form and the anatase form are photoactive(47). Sunscreens without nanoparticles were heavy formulations that were unsightly and did not blend well with the skin, due to the presence of zinc oxide (ZnO) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) which are the two most popular components in sunscreens. To overcome this in the last few years manufacturers began employing the nanoscale TiO₂(50). Most of the commercial sunscreen powders that contained ZnO and/or TiO₂, none of which had any information on size on the label(48). The systemically accessible dose of TiO₂ (epidermis, dermis, and receptor fluid) in the derma to medium pig skin exposed to 760 µg/cm² and 816 µg/cm² titanium in UV-filters was <0.081 ± 0.071% and 0.048 ± 0.030%, respectively, according to the 2017 report from the European Commission Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety. The particle Ti infiltrates healthy skin during a 24-hour exposure, showing, titanium clusters in the dermis, the epidermis, and the vicinity of hair follicles but was not confined to the SC(49). According to a social survey carried out in Wisconsin, USA, people who come into contact with personal care products on their skin are exposed to 2.8–21.38 mg of TiO₂ on an average day. Sunscreen, toothbrush, and body wash are the main sources of exposure, 181.8 mg per day is the maximum exposure that can occur(46). Pilot study has been conducted to determine the percutaneous absorption of microfine titanium dioxide by selecting patients to have a skin surgery, 2-6 weeks prior to the surgery the patients applied titanium dioxide sunscreen regularly. The result from this pilot study shows the level of titanium dioxide in the dermis and epidermis is higher than the control level, but further studies are necessary to determine the statistical significance(51). Titanium dioxide + defensil are given to the group from 1 -7 days, there is significant decrease in the melanin index and also gradual decrease in the erythema index(52).

6.5 ZINC OXIDE

Using sunscreen reduces the negative impacts of UVA (320–400 nm) and UVB (290–320 nm) radiation exposure. The US Food and Drug Administration states that at least one-third of the total factor for sun protection should come from UVA protection. Minerals like titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO) are commonly found in sunscreens as inorganic physical sun blockers. The combination of these particles offers broad-spectrum UV defence. Since ZnO is more potent in the UVA area and TiO₂ works well in UVB wavelengths. Nevertheless, TiO₂ and ZnO microsized particles have been gradually replaced with TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles (NPs), which have a size of 100 nm, To tackle the aesthetic concern of these opaque sunscreens(54). The two primary categories of active components included in modern sunscreens are "chemical" and "physical". Typically, the active "physical" components are particles of metal oxides, such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO), which have natural UV-absorbing properties. which reflect and scatter light within the typical ranges of pigment sizes(150–300 nm for TiO₂ and 200–400 nm for ZnO). This particles gives the characteristic white look of sunscreens(53). In 2005, there were 308 sunscreen creams available for skin application in the UK, with a sun protection factor (SPF) values ranging from 2 to 60 (median 20). (Wahie, Lloyd, and Farr 2007). Eleven products (3.6%) contained TiO₂ and/or ZnO but no chemical UV filters, whereas 169 items (54.8%) were composed of chemical UV absorbers but lacked these components. For the remaining 128 items (41.6%), a combination with chemical absorbing materials and metal oxide reflectance was applied. The study discovered that ZnO and TiO₂ particles were preferably one of the active ingredients in around half of the sunscreens that were sold commercially. Under some conditions, like the high temperature of UV radiation, ZnO is chemically stable compared to bulk-sized compounds, the NP's large surface area-to-volume ratios

increase its ability to block UV radiation(55). Using variable angle spectroscopic ellipsometry, Sun and Kwok discovered values for the optical refractive indices in the 375–900 nm range. The values roughly ranging from 2.3 to 2.0.40. As a result, ZnO has less whitening impact than TiO₂(54). This causes the average particle size of a metal oxide to be decreased below the optimal light scattering size, allowing visible light to flow across which makes the oxide appear nearly unnoticeable on skin. This feature has been employed to generate the microfine metal oxide levels that are now frequently discovered in sunscreen as well as daily skin care products. To help in dispersion, zinc oxide, or TiO₂, is frequently coated with other substances like silicones, fatty acids, or oxides of silicon, aluminum, or zirconium. Sunscreen creams' active component is titanium dioxide(56). The covering Zinc oxide-containing sunscreens offer comprehensive safeguards against the recognized cancer-causing, suppressive of immunity, and premature aging damage caused by UVA and UVB light(53). Conversely, ZnO is "widely accepted as effective" by the Food and Drug Administration when used as a UV filter in accordance with cosmetics regulations(54). Based on safeguarding paperwork, the Working Group on Beauty products of the European Union (EU) Commission has concluded that there is no possibility of adverse health effects for individuals when cosmetic products containing nanosized ZnO and TiO₂ are applied topically up to a 25% level. Additionally, a comprehensive review ordered by the Danish Environment Ministry has shown that externally applied small particles are probably to get through the skin in most cases, though in some cases they may little do so(57).

7.APPLICATION

Continuous and routine use of sunscreen decreases the risk of development of Actinic keratitis (AK), cancer of the skin, tumours of squamous cells (SCC), and sun damage(72,73). Sunscreens lessen the likelihood that experimentally caused cancers in animals exposed to UV radiation may occur.(7) There is insufficient evidence to conclusively prove that sunscreen filters are harmful to people. Significant systemic absorption shouldn't be a problem because the SC seems to be a reliable barrier against the penetration of inorganic zinc and titanium dioxide nano particulates. The danger of photoallergy is the most frequent side effect of using chemical sun screens, albeit it is not very prevalent overall(74). Regular SPF 15+ sunscreen application during a 5-year period appears to minimize the incidence of new primary melanomas in adults aged 25 to 75 for up to 10 years after the study's termination, according to the long-term follow-up of this randomized trial(75). 50% of every cancer diagnosis in the United States are skin cancers. In a 4.5-year randomly controlled experiment in an Australian population, regular use of sunscreen on the head, neck, hands, and forearms has been shown to avoid the development of squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) but not basal cell carcinomas (BCC)(76). Although sunscreens are widely promoted for preventing skin cancer in humans and are easily accessible, it remains unknown whether their use actually reduces the events other than melanoma or melanoma skin cancer in humans. Consistent use of sunscreens helps prevent the formation of solar keratoses and may potentially lower the long-term risk of skin cancer(77). The cautious daily use of broad-ranging protection products with good UVA protection won't lower vitamin D levels in people in good health(78).

8.CONCLUSION

This paper high lights the effectiveness of the main ingredients in the sunscreen life zinc oxide, titanium dioxide, octocrylene, avobenzene.as we conclude that continuous use sunscreen protect the skin from the sun damage and other skin related disease conditions and does not produce any adverse reactions by the regular use sunscreen.

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